

STUDY OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN RELATION TO MENTAL HEALTH AND FAMILY ENVIRONMENT OF PRIMARY LEVEL STUDENTS

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Abstract

In the Modern age of Competition and perfection, every human being strives for success. The factor like Academic achievement, Mental health, and Family environment, plays a significant role in the attainment of the ideal and harmonious development of the child. Academic achievement is the status of an individual's learning and his ability to apply what he has learned. In addition, the concept of mental health is as old as human beings. Further, Mental health problems in early childhood increase the risk of poor academic performance because nurturing a family is a corner store of positive mental well-being (Kayne Hodge, 2023). Family plays a very significant role in the all-round development of the child. Parent-child interaction and parents' way to be with their children, develop certain attitudes among the children towards their family environment. In recent years clinical psychologists, as well as educators, have started giving proper attention to the study of mental health, family environment, and academic achievement. The present study was conducted on the study of academic achievement in relation to the family environment and mental health among primary-level students. The study has been conducted on the students of primary school and was confined to 140 students of 4th class only in Gurdaspur, only to know the relationship between family environment mental health and academic achievement among the students of primary level.

KEYWORDS: Family Environment, Mental Health, Academic Achievement, Primary Level Students

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INTRODUCTION

Mental health concerns everyone. It affects our ability to cope with and manage change, life events, and transitions such as bereavement or retirement. All human beings have mental health needs, no matter what the state of their psyche. Mental health needs can be met in a variety of settings including acute hospital settings, primary care settings, self-help groups, social services, and of course through counselling and psychotherapy. Mental health and mental illness can be thought of as a continuum, rather than a polarised dichotomy, with people

positioned at various points depending on life events (external factors), genetic inheritance, and stages of development (internal factors). There are many definitions of mental health, the majority of which are simplistic, partial, and inevitably subjective. Tudor (2004) argues that it is more helpful to think in terms of concepts of mental health and illness. Tudor (1996) described mental health as multifaceted with six dimensions: affective, behavioral, cognitive, spiritual, socio-political, and psychological. The Mental Health Foundation stated that an individual with good mental health is defined as one who can:

1. Develop emotionally, creatively, intellectually, and spiritually;
2. Initiate, develop, and sustain mutually satisfying personal relationships;
3. Face problems, resolve them, and learn from them;
4. Be confident and assertive;
5. Be aware of others and empathize with them;
6. Use and enjoy solitude;
7. Play and have fun;
8. Laugh, both at themselves and at the world.

Moreover, Jahoda (1958) who identified categories, within which concepts of mental health could be represented. He described these as follows:

1. Mental health is indicated by the attitudes of the individual toward themselves
2. Mental health is expressed in the individual's style and degree of growth, development, or self-actualization
3. Mental health is based on the individual's relation to reality in terms of autonomy, perception of reality, environmental mastery
4. Mental health is the ability of the individual to integrate developing and differing aspects of themselves over time.

Apart from this, the World Health Organization (WHO) defines mental health as a state of well-being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to her or his community (World Health Organization 2014). The positive dimension of mental health stressed in the WHO's definition of health is contained in its constitution as "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity." Mental health may be described in another way as a continuum (Sands 2001) where "an individual is more or less functional with respect to different activities. A person may function at a relatively high level in some areas (manages own apartment, uses transportation),

but at the dysfunctional level in others (interpersonal relationships, employment).”

Furthermore, the importance of Mental Health and well-being, especially among school-going students has been acknowledged by NEP, 2020. The policy highlights the concern of mental health issues, among students. Mental health is Linked with all the aspects of health i.e., physical, social, and emotional. Mental health is extremely important in schools as this has an important role to play in supporting students to enable a state of well-being, where students can meet their learning potential, cope with stress, and openly connect with their friends and community. Further, in this, context Ministry of Education under the Atam Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan, launched an initiative, ‘manodarpan’, to address the mental health and well-being concerns of students (Manodarpan Cell-NCERT, 2022). This has become a major concern because the focus of NEP, 2020 highlights the urgent need for ensuring not only cognitive development but also building character and creating holistic and well-rounded individuals equipped with 21st-century skills. And, sound mental health and well-being of students create the foundational base for holistic development and nurturance of students, and for imparting life skills that assist them in their growth, self-preservation, and sustainable development.

In addition to this, Academic achievement is also one of the most important outcomes of formal educational experiences and while there is little doubt as to the vital role such achievements play in student life and later (Kell et al., 2013), researchers and policymakers are ever increasingly turning to social and emotional factors, as well as the relationships among them, as indicators of student well-being and psychological development (Chernyshenko et al., 2018; Frydenberg et al., 2017). Indicative of this movement is the recent addition of social and emotional measures to established Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) measures (OECD, 2019). These measures include, according to Chernyshenko et al. (2018), emotional regulation (e.g., stress resistance, optimism), task performance (e.g., motivation, persistence, self-control), and compound skills (e.g., metacognition, self-efficacy). Consistent with this theme, you will find six quality empirical studies in this Issue that examine some of the complexities of such factors, some related to academic achievement, and others not, having legitimacy in their own right.

Academic achievement has been playing an important role in the studies by Colmar et al., (2019) and Martinez et al., (2019). For Colmaret al. (2019), the capacity of elementary school students to respond to academic setbacks, and academic buoyancy, was not predictive of academic achievement. However, academic buoyancy effects were demonstrated for both reading and mathematics achievement in Australian students when mediated by self-concept.

Moreover, efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience are foregrounded in Martinez et al. (2019) examination of Spanish/Portuguese university students' engagement and achievement. This shows that students who report being engaged in learning are more likely to be users of psychological capital who in turn are more likely to achieve higher academically.

Academic achievement is integrated also into the work of Eakman, et al., (2019), where the focus is on the complexities of the emotional and social lives of returned veterans and service personnel. In a comprehensive study, learning climate support, post-traumatic stress, depression, self-efficacy, and academic problems are linked to achievement showing, among other findings, that self-efficacy, fewer academic problems, and autonomy supporting learning environments are positively related to achievement. Moreover, these factors persisted irrespective of depression or post-traumatic stress levels. Thus, psychological, environmental, and social factors play an influential role in the academic achievement of students.

Moreover, the study review of researches highlights that many studies have been conducted on the students at secondary school level, High school level, Middle school level, University level, rural students, urban students, and hilly students in relation to mental health and academic achievement (Barmola, 2013; Bas, 2020; Singh, 2015; Kumar and Sahu, 2019; Khatoon & Sharma, 2021; Singh & Goswami), family environment and academic achievement (Barmola, 2013; Khatoon & Sharma, 2021; Zhao & Zhao, 2022), mental health and family environment (Barmola, 2013; Roudriguez et al., 2014; Singh & Yadav, 2019) but not even a single study has been conducted on the students of primary school level. This emphasizes the significance of understanding the relationship between mental health and family environment on the academic achievement of primary-level students.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

STUDY OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN RELATION TO FAMILY ENVIRONMENT, AND MENTAL HEALTH OF PRIMARY LEVEL STUDENTS

OBJECTIVES

1. To know the relationship between family environment, and mental health of primary school students.
2. To know the relationship between family environment and academic achievement of primary school students.
3. To know the relationship between mental health and academic achievement of primary school students.

HYPOTHESES

Present Investigation has been designed to achieve the following Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant relationship between family environment and mental health in primary school students.
2. There is no significant relationship between family environment and academic achievement in primary school students.
3. There is no significant relationship between mental health and academic achievement in primary school students.

RESEARCH METHOD

Sample:

The sample for the present study has been taken using a Random sampling technique, based on which 140 students from 2 private primary schools and 2 government primary schools have been selected.

Design of the study:

The study falls under the domain of descriptive survey research as it intends to study academic achievement in relation to mental health and the family environment of primary school students.

Procedure:

The study has been conducted on 140 students of the 4th class from private and govt. schools in the Gurdaspur district. After selecting the sample, academic achievement (of the previous class), Family environment scale

(Shah Beena, 2011) and Mental health scale (Singh, A. K., 2012) have been administered to the selected students. The collected data have been scored and statistical techniques have been employed.

MEASURES USED

The following tools have been used as a measure to get the required information:

1. Family Environment Scale (Adapted by an investigator from the family environment scale prepared by Shah Beena, 2011).
2. Mental health scale (Adapted by an investigator from the Mental Health scale prepared by Singh A. K., 2012)
3. Previous Class Result record of students (from the school Authorities).

Statistical Techniques

Following statistical techniques have been used to analyze the data;

1. Descriptive statistics techniques such as mean, standard deviation, has been used to see the nature of distribution of the scores.
2. T-test has been applied to determine the significant difference between groups with respect to gender and type of school.
3. Correlation has been calculated to see the relationship among the three variables.

1. SIGNIFICANCE OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND MENTAL HEALTH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

TABLE1 : Showing Pearson Correlation between Family Environment and Mental health

Variable	Mental health Score	
	Pearson correlation	0.850**
	Sig.(2 tailed)	0.000
Family environment Score	N	140

From table 1 it is clear that the value of Pearson correlation between family environment and mental health is found to be 0.850**. And the p-value is found to be 0.000 which is less than the p-value at 0.05 level of significance which means that there exists a ***positive and significant relationship between family environment and mental health***. Hence, the null hypothesis “*There is no significant relationship between family environment and mental health in primary school students*” is ***not accepted***. It means a healthy family environment leads to healthy mental health.

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FAMILY ENVIRONMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

TABLE2 : Showing Pearson Correlation between Family Environment and Academic Achievement

Variable	Academic Achievement	
	Pearson correlation	0.923**
	Sig (2 tailed)	0.000
Family environment Score	N	140

From the above table, it is clear that the value of Pearson correlation between family environment and academic achievement is found to be 0.923**. And the p-value is found to be 0.000 which is less than the p-value at 0.05 level of significance which means that there exists a **positive and significant relationship between family environment and academic achievement**. Hence, the null hypothesis framed to ascertain that “*There is no significant relationship between family environment and Academic Achievement in primary school students*” is not accepted. It means a healthy family environment leads to good academic achievement.

3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MENTAL HEALTH AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

TABLE 3 Showing Pearson Correlation between Academic Achievement and Mental Health

Variable	Academic Achievement	
	Pearson correlation	0.882**
	Sig.(2 tailed)	0.000
Mental Health Score	N	140

From the above table it is clear that the value of Pearson correlation between family environment and academic achievement is found to be 0.882**. And the p-value is found to be 0.000 which is less than the p-value at 0.05 level of significance which means that there exists **positive and significant relationship between mental health and academic achievement**. Hence null hypothesis “*There is no significant relationship between Mental Health Score and Academic Achievement in primary school students*” is not accepted. It means healthy mental health leads to good academic achievement.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The major findings related to the present study reveal that there exists a positive and significant relationship between family environment and mental health that is inconsistent with the study of Barmola (2013), the result of which suggests the existence of a significant relationship between family environment and mental health, and academic performance mental health. Further, the present study also highlights there was a positive and significant relationship between family environment and mental health, which is consistent with the study of reveals that a poor family environment leads to more mental health problems. Furthermore, there

exists a positive and significant relationship between family environment and academic achievement which is consistent with Zhao & Zhao (2022). In addition, the findings also reveal the existence of a positive and significant relationship between mental health and academic achievement that is consistent with the study of Bas (2020), Singh (2015), Jenkins (2019), and White, (2016). Overall, the result of the study completely reveals building a healthy family environment and mental health so that students can progress and have better academic achievement.

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